

Evaluation of arrayed primer extension for *TP53* mutation detection in breast and ovarian carcinomas

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Mutations in the tumor suppressor gene TP53 are associated with a wide range of different cancers and may have prognostic and therapeutic implications. Methods for rapid and sensitive detection of mutations in this gene are therefore required. In order to make screening more effective, a commercially available TP53 genotyping microarray from Asper Biotech has been constructed by arrayed primer extension (APEX). The present study is the first report that blindly evaluates the efficiency of the second generation APEX TP53 genotype chip outside the Asper laboratory and compares it to temporal temperature gradient electrophoresis (TTGE) and sequencing of TP53 for mutation detection in ovarian and breast cancer samples. All nucleotides in the TP53 gene from exon 2–9 are included on the chip by synthesis and application of sequence-specific oligonucleotides. The chip was validated by screening 48 breast and 11 ovarian cancer cases, all of which had previously been analyzed by TTGE and sequencing. APEX scored 17 of 20 sequence variants, missing one deletion, one insertion, and a missense mutation. Resequencing efficiency using APEX was 92% for both DNA strands and 99.5% for sense and/or antisense strand. We conclude that the APEX TP53 microarray is a robust, rapid, and comprehensive screening tool for sequence alterations in tumors.

INTRODUCTION

Somatic alterations in the tumor suppressor gene *TP53* are the most frequent findings in a wide range of different cancers. In breast tumors, around 30% of the cases are found to have a mutated *TP53* gene (1), and the presence of an alteration has been associated with unfavorable prognosis (2–4). It has also been shown that breast cancer patients with specific *TP53* mutations have different responses to therapy (5–10). Thus, screening and identification of mutations in this gene may have important implications for prognosis and cancer treatment.

A variety of screening methods are currently in use, all of which have limitations regarding sensitivity, specificity, cost, or amount of work needed for detection of mutations (11,12). Screening of the *TP53* gene is a laborious task, as many of the tumor samples have low amount of mutated cells caused by infiltrating nontumor cells or large clonal variation within the tumor. Mutations that affect *TP53* activity may therefore easily be missed. This leads to an incomplete knowledge of the effect of these mutations on tumor aggressiveness and chemoresistance. It is important to detect these mutations as early as possible during tumor formation in order to select the proper therapy. This implies that methods that are fast,

reliable, cost-effective, and have a high sensitivity should be applied.

In the current study, we used an arrayed primer extension (APEX) assay to identify mutations in the *TP53* gene in 48 cases with primary breast cancer. The arrays are commercially available and were designed by Asper Biotech (www.asperbio.com; Tartu, Estonia). All samples were screened blindly and compared with the results obtained from temporal temperature gradient electrophoresis (TTGE) followed by direct sequencing of the aberrant migrating bands. Eleven late-stage high-grade ovarian cancer cases positive for p53 immunohistochemistry (IHC) staining but negative after an initial TTGE screening were also included in this study and screened by APEX followed by sequencing and a second TTGE.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Patient Material

Tumor samples in this study came from 48 primary breast carcinomas and 11 patients with advanced ovarian carcinomas. All patients had primary surgery, and tumor tissues

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obtained immediately after surgery were snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen. Formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tissue from each patient was used for IHC. All tumors had been classified and graded based on World Health Organization (WHO) criteria. Hematoxylin and eosin-stained sections were used to evaluate the percentage of tumor cells. The range of tumor cells in the breast cancer samples was from a few percent to 100% with a median of 60%, and the range of ovarian tumor cells was from 20% to 90% with a median of 70%. DNA was isolated from tumor tissue using chloroform/phenol extraction followed by ethanol precipitation (Model 340A nucleic acid extractor; Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA) according to standard procedures.

DNA Arrays

The APEX assay is performed in two dimensions on a glass array of oligonucleotides immobilized via the 5' end. The oligonucleotides are attached to the surface of the slide in a grid, and each nucleotide of exon 2–9 in the *TP53* gene is identified by two unique 25-mer oligonucleotides, one each for the sense and the antisense strand. PCR products are denatured and annealed to the oligonucleotide primers flanking the nucleotides to be identified. The primers are extended by DNA polymerase using four different fluorescent-labeled terminator nucleotides. Each of the terminators identifies one base in the target sequence (for more information go to www.asperbio.com/APEX.htm).

PCR and DNA Fragmentation

Exon 2–9 of the *TP53* gene were amplified from genomic DNA in three products using PCR. The 25- μ L PCR contained 10 \times PCR buffer [800 mM Tris-HCl, pH 9.4–9.5, 200 mM (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.2% Tween[®] 20; Solis Biodyne, Tartu, Estonia], 2.5 mM MgCl₂, dNTP-mixture (2.5 mM dATP, dCTP, dGTP, 2.0 mM dTTP, and 0.5 mM dUTP; Applied Biosystems), 1 U Hot FirePol[®] DNA polymerase (Solis Biodyne), 50–100 ng genomic DNA, and 20–50 pmol of each primer. For more information about primers and product size, see Table 1. All PCRs were performed with an initial step of DNA polymerase activation for 15 min at 95°C, followed by 35 cycles of 95°C for 20 s, 62°C for 30 s, and 72°C for 40 s. A final elongation step for 10 min at 72°C was added. The products were purified using Jet Quick Spin Columns (GenoMed, St. Louis, MO, USA). Inactivation of unincorporated dNTPs and fragmentation of the products were performed by adding 1 U shrimp alkaline phosphatase (United States Biochemical, Cleveland, OH, USA) and 2 U thermolabile uracil *N*-glycosylase (UNG; Epicenter Technologies, Madison, WI, USA) and heated at 37°C for 60 min followed by UNG inactivation at 95°C for 10 min (13).

Resequencing by APEX

The arrays were pretreated before use by a quick dip in 95°C Milli-Q[®] water (Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA) followed by a 100 mM NaOH wash for 10 min and three final washes in 95°C Milli-Q water for 2 min. The APEX reaction

Table 1. Primers Used for the APEX Method

Primer	Exon	Size (bp)	Strand
5'-TGGAAGTGTCTCATGCTGGA-3'	Two - 4	704	Sense
5'-ATACGGCCAGGCATTGAAGT-3'			Antisense
5'-TCTGTCTCCTTCTCCTCCT-3'	Five - 6	456	Sense
5'-CACTGACAACCACCCCTTAAC-3'			Antisense
5'-CCTGCTTGCCACAGGTCT-3'	Seven - 9	1020	Sense
5'-GCCCCAATTGCAGGTAAAAC-3'			Antisense

APEX, arrayed primer extension.

consisted of 21–25 μ L Milli-Q water, 6–10 μ L fragmented DNA, 5 U (35 U/ μ L) Thermo Sequenase[™] DNA polymerase (Amersham Biosciences, Little Chalfont, Buckinghamshire, UK) diluted in 4 μ L 10 \times Thermo Sequenase reaction buffer (supplied with the DNA polymerase), and 1 μ L (50 μ M) of each fluorescent labeled ddNTP: Texas Red[®], ddATP; Cy[™]3, ddCTP; fluorescein, ddGTP; and Cy5, ddUTP (Amersham Biosciences). The DNA/water mixture was denatured at 95°C for 10 min. Enzyme, dye terminators, and buffer were added immediately to the other components and applied to the prewarmed arrays on a heat-plate. The arrays were covered with coverslips, wet paper, and a lid to prevent desiccation. The hybridization and APEX reaction were performed at 58°C for 15 min and terminated by washing at 95°C for 1 min in Milli-Q water, followed by washing for 3 min in 0.5% Alconox[®] solution (Alconox, White Plains, NY, USA). Alconox was removed by washing the arrays two times for 1 min with 95°C Milli-Q water. To reduce bleaching, 16 μ L Molecular Probes[™] *SlowFade*[®] antifade reagent (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) were applied to the slide. The arrays were scanned with the Genorama[®] imaging system (Asper Biotech) at 20 μ m resolution. All samples were successfully analyzed at least twice with identical results.

Normalization of Samples

The current analysis software supports signal normalization in APEX in three different ways. All the three different ways of signal normalization were used in this study, and they primarily affect the visual intensity of the dots and amount of background. The first and simplest way to normalize is by the signal maximum value. The most intense signal in each of the images is given the same value (1000), and the values of the remaining signals are proportionally multiplied or divided by the same factor. This gives the highest amount of visual sensitivity but also the highest background.

The second way of normalizing the samples is by the weakest nucleotide. The hundred most intense signals from each of the images are selected as a reference for comparison. The average values for this set of signals are compared, and all signals from three images (except the one with the smallest average value) will be divided by the variable from the comparison of the 100 most intense signals.

Normalization by distribution of signals is the third way and assumes that the signal intensity histograms must

Table 2. Mutations Scored by APEX and TTGE in 48 Breast Cancer Samples

Sample ID	Mutation			Scored by		Tumor Cells (%)	p53 Status ^a
	Exon	Nucleotide Change	Amino Acid Change	TTGE	APEX		
ITAM 036	4	108G>A	Pro36Pro	+	+	10	+
ITAM 198	4	207delT	Ala69fs	+	-	70	-
ITAM 339	5	402insT	Phe134fs	+	-	10	-
ITAM 402	5	469G>T	Val157Phe	-	+	80	++
ITAM 151	5	497C>A	Ser166X	+	+	60	-
ITAM 345	5	533_538del5	His178_ His179fs	+	+	80	-
ITAM 059	5	535C>T	His179Tyr	+	+	80	+++
ITAM 164	6	639A>G	Arg213Arg	+	+	20	-
ITAM 185	6	639A>G	Arg213Arg	+	+	40	-
ITAM 347	7	722C>G	Ser241Cys	+	-	40	+++
ITAM 259	8	824G>T	Cys275Phe	+	+	70	+++
ITAM 136	8	832C>G	Pro278Ala	+	+	70	++
	6	639A>G	Arg213Arg	+	+		
ITAM 119	8	916C>T	Arg306X	-	+	5	-

IHC, immunohistochemistry; APEX, arrayed primer extension; TTGE, temporal temperature gradient electrophoresis.
^aIHC staining for p53 (percentage of cells positive for p53): -, no staining; +, <10%; ++, 10%–50%; +++, >50%.

be equal between different images. All signals from each image are rated (1st, 2nd, 3rd, etc.). Signals with the same number in the sequence are compared, and the more intense signal values adjusted to the level of the signal value from the weakest image (e.g., the second strongest signal from the A, C, and T images must have the same value as the second strongest from the G image). This gives the lowest background, but also shows a lower intensity in weak spots (Genorama Genotyping Software Guide; additional questions on the software can be addressed to info@asperbio.com or www.asperbio.com).

TTGE and Sequencing

Amplification of exons 2–9 of the *TP53* gene for analyses by TTGE was performed according to previously published protocols (14). All samples showing aberrant migrating bands were sequenced starting from the new PCR product. Primers and conditions for both TTGE and sequencing were as described by Sørli et al. (14). Sequencing of the ovarian cancer samples was performed using the PCR products generated according to the APEX protocol. The sequence reaction was carried out using a dideoxy-sequencing reaction and Dye Terminator Cycle Sequencing kit with AmpliTaq[®] FS and analyzed on an ABI PRISM[®] 377 DNA Sequencer or an ABI PRISM 310 Genetic Analyzer (all from Applied Biosystems) according to the manufacturer's protocol. When the mutated versus wild-type DNA ratio was low, sequencing

of aberrant bands from TTGE was performed.

Immunohistochemistry

For breast carcinomas samples, immunohistochemical staining for p53 was performed on tumor samples, using 4- μ m-thick sections from formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded material upon heat-induced epitope retrieval. Slides were incubated with primary antibody mouse monoclonal DO-7 (Dako, Glostrup, Denmark) at a 1:100 dilution overnight. The immunoreaction was enhanced by the streptavidin-biotin-peroxidase technique, followed by counterstaining with Carazzi hematoxylin. Immunostaining was assessed using light microscopy. Diffuse or dot-like nuclear reactivity in >10% of the tumor cells was considered positive staining.

Ovarian sample sections for IHC were stained using the Dako EnVision[™] + System, peroxidase diaminobenzidine (DAB), and the Dako autostainer (all from DakoCytomation, Carpinteria, CA, USA). Only distinct nuclear staining was considered positive. Four semiquantitative classes were used to describe the number of positively stained tumor cells: (-) none, (+) less than 10% of the cells, (++) 10%–50% of the cells, and (+++) more than 50% of the cells. Tumors were defined as positive if more than 10% of the cells were positive for p53.

RESULTS

Breast Cancer Cases

The breast carcinoma samples were screened in parallel in blinded experiments using the described APEX method and the TTGE method, followed by direct sequencing of aberrant migrating bands. The results from the two methods were then compared. A total of 14 genetic alterations were scored in 13 of the 48 breast cancer cases giving a frequency of 27% (Table 2). Five missense mutations, four silent mutations (3 in codon 213), one 5-bp deletion, one 1-bp deletion, one 1-bp insertion, and two nonsense mutations were identified. Twelve cases had one sequence change, and one case had two changes (sample ITAM 136). One missense and one nonsense mutation identified by APEX were not detected by TTGE. Three mutations (a deletion, an insertion, and a missense mutation) were not scored by APEX (Table 2 and Figure 1). The codon 72 polymorphisms (CGC to CCC, Arg to Pro) were detected by both methods; 19 of the samples

were heterozygous and 5 were hemi- or homozygous for the rare Pro allele. All sequence changes were confirmed by sequencing.

Ovarian Cancer Cases

Eleven advanced ovarian carcinomas positive for p53 by IHC, but negative after an initial TTGE screening, were also included in this study. These cases were screened by APEX followed by dideoxy sequencing of exon 2–9, both sense and antisense strand, as well as a second TTGE. A total of six sequence alterations—four missense mutations, one in-frame deletion, and one frameshift deletion—were identified in six cases (Table 3). Rescreening by TTGE showed aberrant migrating bands in two samples with missense mutations and in one sample with an in-frame deletion, but failed to identify one of the two sequence alterations that were present in a hemi- or homozygote state and two mutations residing close to the TTGE primer or in a critical melting domain.

Slide Quality

Screening of *TP53* by APEX was performed with three different slide batches. The batches had some differences in number of valid signal spots. A signal spot consists of four subspots, two representing the sense and two representing the antisense strand. One batch (E1024) had 10 out of 1055 (0.95%) dead signal spots and 117 (11.09%) signal spots with information from the sense or antisense strand only. The array on this batch had close to 88% good signal spots. Another batch (E1017) had 6 (0.57%) dead signal spots, 77 (7.30%) signal spots with information from the sense or antisense strand, resulting in close to 92.0% good signal spots. The last batch (F0316) had 1 dead signal spot (0.1%), 20 signal spots (1.9%) with information from the sense or antisense strand, and 98% good signal spots. This gives an average of 92% resequencing of both strands and 99.5% resequencing of sense and/or antisense strand.

p53 Staining and Mutation Status in Breast Cancer Cases

IHC has the potential to detect p53 mutations since the mutant protein accumulates in the cell nuclei. A positive p53 immunostain with varying degree of intensity was seen in 15 of 48 breast cancer cases (31%), suggesting the presence of a mutation. Of the thirteen sequence positive tumors, seven exhibited negative IHC reactions, of which three were frameshifts, two were stop codon mutations, and two were silent. The remaining six patients with positive IHC carried silent and/or missense mutations; three samples with 100%, two samples with 20%, and one sample with 1%–2% positive cells. Further, of the nine IHC-positive tumors negative after

Table 3. Mutations Scored by APEX in 11 Ovarian Cancer Samples

Sample Identification	Exon	Mutation		TTGE ^a	APEX	Tumor Cells (%)
		cDNA Nucleotides	Amino Acid Change			
Ov 3917	5	467G>C	Arg156Pro	-	+	35
Ov 3618	6	578A>G	His193Arg	+	+	65
Ov 4589 ^a	6	584T>A	Ile195Asn	-	+	90
Ov 3581	6	659A>G	Tyr220Cys	+	+	80
Ov 3447	8	784delG	Gly262fs	-	+	85
Ov 4713 ^b	8	783_809del	Gly262_ Phe270del	+	+	65

APEX, arrayed primer extension; TTGE, temporal temperature gradient electrophoresis.
^aResults from second screening. All mutations confirmed by sequencing.
^bHemi- or homozygous sequence changes.

Table 4. An Overview of IHC Positive Breast Carcinomas Related to Mutation Status

IHC		Mutation Status ^a		Sum
		+	-	
+		6 ^b	9	15
-		5	28	33
	Sum	11	37	48

^aOnly mutations with a functional consequence (not silent mutations) are included.
^bOne sample had a deletion in exon 10, which is not included in the APEX array.
 IHC, immunohistochemistry; APEX, arrayed primer extension.

Figure 1. Representative results from APEX-based sequencing assay, TTGE, and sequencing. (A) APEX failed to detect the deletion of a thymine in ITA 198, which was scored both by TTGE and sequencing. (B) C to T transition leading to a missense mutation in ITA 59 is an example of a sequence change scored by both techniques. Note that the APEX sense strand gives visually weak signal. (C) C to T transition in sample ITA 119 resulting in a missense mutation was scored by APEX but not by TTGE. APEX, arrayed primer extension; TTGE, temporal temperature gradient electrophoresis.

Table 5. Results from Titration of the Arg/Arg and Pro/Pro Allele on Codon 72 in the TP53 Gene

Sample	Signal strength				Strand	Histograms
	A	C	G	T		
Arg/Arg	2	0	126	0	Sense	
	0	18	0	0	Antisense	
Pro/Pro	0	36	0	0	Sense	
	3	0	89	0	Antisense	
20%	0	13	114	0	Sense	
	5	17	49	0	Antisense	
10%	0	6	106	0	Sense	
	3	15	24	0	Antisense	
5%	0	4	87	0	Sense	
	3	11	15	0	Antisense	
1%	0	0	80	0	Sense	
	3	15	12	0	Antisense	

The Arg/Arg and Pro/Pro genotypes are mixed in the 20%, 10%, 5%, and 1% samples with the fraction of the Pro/Pro allele being decreased.

APEX resequencing of exon 2–9, one had a deletion in exon 10. This gives a 45% (5 out of 11) false negative frequency for detecting functional mutations with IHC and a 24% (9 out of 37) false positive rate for scoring a mutation. For a summary see Table 4.

DISCUSSION

In recent reports, APEX has been shown to be accurate, with full concordance on repeated analyses, and to have a high sensitivity in detecting low amounts of mutated DNA in the presence of wild-type DNA (13,15,16). In contrast to the study by Tönisson et al. (13), in which screening was performed with normal DNA, this study evaluated DNA from tumor samples. The potential of this method for mutation screening led us to investigate whether APEX could match the high sensitivity, specificity, and high-throughput of TTGE as a prescreening method prior to sequencing.

Tumors from 48 patients with primary breast carcinomas were screened blindly using the TTGE strategy, which has been widely used for mutation detection in *TP53*. In addition, eleven advanced high-grade ovarian cancer cases, negative after initial TTGE screening but positive for p53 staining, were investigated. Such samples are routinely rescreened by TTGE in our laboratory, but here we subjected the samples to screening by APEX and sequencing prior to a second screening by TTGE. The samples had a varying percentage of tumor cells, and based on visual inspection, this percentage

ranged from a few percent to 100%.

Our results showed that APEX scored mutations in samples with as little as 5% tumor cells. This level of sensitivity was confirmed in a titration experiment where samples homozygous for the Arg/Arg and Pro/Pro polymorphism in codon 72 of the *TP53* gene were mixed in a 1%, 5%, 10%, and 20% ratio. The Pro/Pro allele was scored at concentrations of 20%, 10%, and 5%, while the results from the 1% group were less convincing, although the signal strength was well above the background for these samples (Table 5).

Two frameshift mutations, one deletion in sample ITAM 198 with 70% tumor cells and one insertion in ITAM 339 with 10% tumor cells, were scored by TTGE but not by APEX. The possible reason for this is discussed below. One missense mutation in sample ITAM 347 with 40% tumor cells was also missed by APEX. This may be a result of low sensitivity of some of the spots/oligonucleotides in the *TP53* array and/or the nature of the mutation. TTGE did not show an aberrantly migrating band in samples ITAM 119 and ITAM 402 with 5% and 40% tumor cells, respectively. In ITAM 402, the mutation was in a critical area in the melting domain of the TTGE products. The heterozygous mutation in ITAM 119 resided in a noncritical area of the melting domain and should have been detected, but was probably missed due to the low percentage of tumor cells (<5%). Previous reports have however shown that TTGE can detect mutations in very low mutant to wild-type DNA ratio—around 10% in homoduplexes and 1%–3% in heteroduplexes (13,17). In TTGE, wild-type and mutant homoduplexes are more difficult to separate than heteroduplexes as a result of smaller differences in migration rates. The fact that we did not score one of the two hemi- or homozygous mutations in the ovarian samples screened with TTGE supports this view. Differences in scoring rates between homozygous and heterozygous mutations were not observed using the APEX technique.

The current method is based on resequencing, and a great advantage is that both strands of the sample DNA are analyzed simultaneously. However, some parts of the *TP53* gene proved to be difficult to analyze from both strands. Signals from one of the strands showed below average performance for parts of some exons in the *TP53* array in general and in exon 7 in particular (13). This may be the result of specific issues with the oligonucleotides such as repeated sequences, regions with high GC content, and self-priming.

The ability to identify deletions and insertions using APEX depends on the neighboring bases. If a nucleotide following a deleted or inserted nucleotide is different from the base deleted and/or inserted, it is possible to detect the deletion and/or insertion. If the following nucleotide is the same as the one deleted or inserted, the mutation will not be detected. Theoretically, if every base occurred randomly and at the same frequency, one out of four deletions or insertions would be missed. When several nucleotides are inserted or deleted, one must take into consideration that both the start and the stop nucleotide must differ from the following base in order to be scored. Thus, if a deletion or insertion is

more than one nucleotide, there is a 1/16 chance of missing the start and stop site, and a 1/4 chance to miss the start or stop site. Consequently, the future challenge for APEX will be to develop additional signal spots representing the most common deletions and/or insertions found in tumor samples.

Despite the high probability of detecting mutations when the following bases were different from that mutated, we were only able to detect one of the four deletions and/or insertions in our material. The 5-bp deletion in ITAM 345 was seen as two transitions 5 bp apart. The first transition was in the second base of codon 178, and the second transition was seen in the third base of codon 179. These DNA changes are, however, easily regarded as two independent events rather than a deletion, until results from sequencing are available. The sense strand deletion of a thymine in codon 69, resulting in a stop in sample ITAM 198, is followed by a guanine. Thus, we should be able to detect a T to G transversion in the sense strand or an A to C transversion in the antisense strand, but this was not the case (Figure 1). The reason for this may be attributed to the oligonucleotides, as discussed above. It would also be an improvement of the array if the most common deletions and insertions in the *TP53* gene could be added as positive controls.

During this study, arrays showing dead spots and spots for one strand only were observed. An average slide had 0.5% dead spots and 7.5% spots with information from the sense or antisense strand only. This gives an average resequencing rate of 92% for both strands and 99.5% from sense and/or antisense strand in the current *TP53* arrays. As spots for one strand only were observed in the same position in the array on different slides, the absence of a spot is probably due to some problems with the oligonucleotides or quality of the slides.

The total number of mutations detected in this evaluation was 20, of which APEX scored 17 and TTGE scored 15. However, four of the five mutations not scored by TTGE resided very close to the primers or in the high melting domain of the TTGE fragment, which may explain why these mutations were missed. Nevertheless, our results show a high correlation between the two methods regarding scoring of DNA changes. To further strengthen the screening capabilities of APEX, the most common mutations, insertions, and deletions should be added to the arrays.

Using the available array to screen for mutations in exon 2–9 of the *TP53* gene, APEX is a fast, reliable, and sensitive method. The sensitivity is close to TTGE, and the accuracy of APEX resequencing is close to 99% for sense and/or antisense strand. This makes APEX suited for screening of *TP53* per se and also suitable as a method to screen for mutations in samples negative after initial TTGE screening.

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COMPETING INTERESTS STATEMENT

The authors declare no competing interests.

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